

NEW SCENARIO FOR RANDOM FRACTAL GROWTH- STUDIES BASED ON DYNAMIC LATTICE LIQUID (DLL) MODEL

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SUMMARY

The dynamic lattice liquid (DLL) model is proposed as a universal tool for investigating various aggregation processes. This model allows to perform simulations in systems with constant number of particles and explicit presence of a solvent. The fractals growth is investigated in the systems with different initial concentration of cluster forming particles. It is shown that fractal dimension increases with increasing initial concentration of particles which build up the cluster. The presented results show that DLL algorithm properly reflects structural and dynamic properties of such process

Keywords: Simulation; Fractals; Crystal Growth; Dynamical Properties

Introduction

Stochastic models of fractal growth have inspired a number of studies and applications in physics, biology, chemistry, nanotechnology, medicine, metallurgy and other domains. The best known model of the fractal growth is the diffusion-limited aggregation model (DLA) which was introduced in the early 1980s by Witten and Sander [1, 2]. It is very popular because it contains the main features of the random growth using a very simple definition. In the DLA model, the initial point for the growing cluster is usually fixed, so that primary cluster consists of a single particle. Every new particle moves according to Brownian motion on regular lattice starting at infinity (or just far enough from the growing cluster). When the particle touches the cluster, it sticks to it irreversibly. The clusters generated by this process are both highly branched and fractal. One can find that the described scenario assumes that the fractal grows in a medium which is an infinitely dilute solution. Moreover in one time quantum (regarded as one particle trail) only one particle can touch the cluster. This generates problem with a time scale and seems to be strange comparing with real situations with finite concentrations of particles. It suggests that a parallel algorithm has to be used to model this kind of process to obtain proper dynamic features.

Many modifications of the DLA scenario were proposed for various problems, like: random walks based cluster-cluster aggregation models [3], reversible aggregation models [4,5], two component system models [6], reaction limited aggregation (RLA) models [7], influence of surface heterogeneity on aggregation process [8], fluctuating diffusion-limited aggregates [9], aggregation of associating polymers [10] and investigation of complexity of diffusion limited aggregation model using parallel random access machine (PRAM) [11]. Each of mentioned modifications concentrates only on some particular aspects of real processes and additionally a time scale introduced in unnatural way results in the problems with dynamic investigations. The dynamic lattice liquid (DLL) model [12], used in this paper, has following main features which can be useful in modeling of aggregation:

- It accounts for the effect of particle interactions by introducing probabilities of attach p_1 and detach p_2 .
- It covers the whole spectrum from DLA ($p_1=1$) to RLA ($p_1 \rightarrow 0$).

- It takes into account molecular structure (the molecules with complex architecture such as: chains, stars etc ... can be simulated)
- It can work on all 2D and 3D regular lattices.
- It takes under consideration explicit presence of a solvent
- It is a strictly parallel model, which allows to introduce time scale in a natural way
- It allows to perform simulation of aggregation in non-homogenous media
- It allows to simulate aggregation in confined geometry in 2D and 3D cases
- It can deal with multi-component mixtures, whereby the components are allowed to behave differently

Moreover, the dynamic behavior of equilibrium and non equilibrium systems [13-16] are very well reflected by the simulations based on the DLL model.

DLL simulation method

The DLL model is based on a lattice structure with beads representing atoms or small molecules located at the lattice sites. The assumption of dense packing of molecules leads to consideration of a system with all the lattice sites occupied by molecules (beads). It is also assumed, that the system has some excess volume, big enough for oscillations of the molecules around their positions defined by the lattice sites. However, the molecules cannot

move individually over larger distances, because all neighboring lattice sites are occupied by similar elements. Nevertheless a long-range cooperative mobility in such system can take place. The DLL model answers the question under which conditions molecular translations over distances exceeding the vibrational range are possible. Each such displacement (on a distance equal a , where a is lattice constant) of the molecule from the mean position is considered as an attempt of a movement to a neighboring lattice site. Directions of the attempts are assumed only along the coordination lines but they are independent and randomly distributed among q directions, where q is the lattice coordination number. Only these attempts can be successful, which coincide with another in such a way that along a path including more than two molecules the sum of displacements is equal to zero (condition of continuity). This results in displacements of beads along self-avoiding closed paths.

A molecular system treated in this way can be regarded as provided with the dynamics consisting of local vibrations and occasional diffusion steps resulting from coincidences of attempts of the neighboring elements to displace beyond the occupied positions. Within longer time interval, this kind of dynamics leads to displacements of individual beads along the random walk trajectories with steps distributed randomly in time.

The model described above has been implemented as a dynamic simulation algorithm for simple liquids in two dimensions. A systems of beads on the triangular lattice is considered. The beads are regarded as representing (substrates) molecules and they occupy all the lattice sites. Attempts to move are represented by a field of randomly chosen unit vectors, which are assigned to beads and point to directions of attempted motions. An example of such assignment of attempted directions of motion is shown in Fig. 1, for a system representing simple liquid on the triangular lattice. All beads, which do not contribute to correlated sequences (loops) in the way satisfying the continuity condition are not displaced in the given step. This occurs in cases 1 and 2 shown in Fig. 1.

If all vectors giving non-successful attempts have been set to zero, only the vectors contributing to of closed loops remain. They constitute traces for the possible rearrangements (case 3 in Fig. 1). If an athermal system is considered, all possible rearrangements are performed by shifting beads along the closed loops, each bead to a neighboring lattice site. Thus, in this algorithm the following steps can be distinguished in one time quantum: (i) generation of the vector field representing attempts of movement, (ii) elimination of non successful attempts and (iii) replacing beads within closed loop paths. The algorithm works in parallel. It means that the set of attempts to move of all beads is considered and the allowed moves are performed simultaneously (parallel).

The stochastic fractal growth process can be readily modeled using the DLL simulation, provided that an appropriate rule is added to take into account the particle-particle aggregation. The system contains two kinds of moving particles: A which build up a fractal cluster with initial concentration ϕ and B -inert solvent with initial concentration $1-\phi$. There are also immobile particles C . At the beginning of the simulation one particle C is introduced to the system to act as an aggregation seed. When diffusing particle A becomes the nearest neighbor of the particle C , they stick. It leads to the cluster growth by transforming a moving A particle into cluster particle C . Because DLL algorithm is parallel several particles can stick at the same time.

The simulations were carried out for systems where concentration of the particles A varied from $\phi=0.03$ to $\phi=0.20$. At the initial moment, the particles A are placed randomly on the two-dimensional triangular lattice with periodic boundary conditions. In all simulations the system contains over 10^6 particles.

Results and discussion

To characterize fractal structure we usually use fractal dimension d_f which is defined by the expression,

$$N(R) = k_0 R^{d_f}, \quad (1)$$

where k_0 is a prefactor of the fractal scaling relationship, R is a characteristic size and $N(R)$ is the number of particles aggregated in cluster. As the characteristic size, radius of gyration is usually used:

$$R_g^2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\vec{r}_{cm} - \vec{r}_i)^2, \quad (2)$$

where \vec{r}_{cm} indicates position of the cluster center of mass and \vec{r}_i is the position of i particle included in the cluster. The characteristic size one can be also express as a mean cluster

Figure 2. Snapshots of a structure fractal grown illustrating as the same area is filled by fractal elements depending on the initial concentration. Initial concentration ϕ , mass, fractal d_f dimension, and growing time are indicated in the figures. Only a central part of the simulated system is shown

radius,

$$R_m = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N |\vec{r}_{cm} - \vec{r}_i| \quad (3)$$

or hydrodynamic radius defined as follows

$$\frac{1}{R_H} = \sum_{i=1}^N \sum_{\substack{j=1 \\ i \neq j}}^N \frac{1}{|\vec{r}_{ij}|} \quad (4)$$

Fig 2 illustrates how the same area is filled by clusters obtained for various initial concentration of particles being a built up units (the figure does not show the whole simulated system, only a part of central region). One can observe that an increase of initial the concentration ϕ leads to the increase of fractal dimension d_f , because the same area is better

Figure 3. Mass of the fractal N as a function of the radius of gyration R_g for various initial concentrations of particles which constitute the cluster.

filled by the elements of the fractal. Figure 3 shows the mass of the cluster N as a function of R_g for various initial concentrations. Using equation 1 the fractal dimension for various initial

Figure 4. Fractal dimension as a function of initial concentration of the particles which constitute the cluster for various characteristic length size: radius of gyration R_g , mean cluster radius R_m and hydrodynamical radius R_H .

concentration ϕ and various specific sizes can be obtained (see Fig. 4). For low concentrations the fractal dimension is near $1.70-1.73$ as expected. This value is generally accepted for the DLA case [17]. For greater concentrations the fractal dimension rapidly increases with increasing concentration. Prefactor k_0 as a function of fractal dimension is shown in Fig. 5. One can observe that k_0 exhibit the same behavior as reported in [18] i.e. k_0 decreases when the fractal dimension increases.

Dynamic scaling of the cluster size is usually discussed using the Smoluchowski coagulation equation [19]. It describes the cluster-size distribution n_l for dilute systems, where only binary collisions are relevant. For long times and large clusters, the number of cluster formed by l elements exhibits dynamic scaling, and the cluster-size distribution approaches the limit form [20]

Figure 5. The prefactor k_0 versus fractal dimension d_f (cf. eq. (1)).

$$n_l(t) \approx N^{-2} \varphi \left(\frac{l}{N} \right) \quad (5)$$

where $N=N(t)$ is related to the number-average cluster size and $\varphi(l/N)$ is an universal time independent cluster size distribution, which characterizes the aggregation mechanism. Using the dynamic scaling equation one can obtain that the fractal characteristic size as a function of time is given by [20]:

$$R(t) \approx t^{\frac{1}{d_f(1-\lambda)}} \quad (6)$$

Combining equation.6 with the fractal scaling relationship (eq. 1) one can obtain number-average mean cluster size as a function of time:

$$N(t) \approx t^{\frac{1}{1-\lambda}} \quad (7)$$

where λ is the van Dongen and Ernst homogeneity exponent which describes different growth kinetics induced by fractal-fractal interaction [21]. It should take the value 0 for diffusion limited cluster aggregation and 1 for reaction limited cluster aggregation.

Fig. 6 presents the mass of the cluster N as a function of time for various initial concentrations ϕ . One can observe that the rate of cluster growth increases rapidly with increasing initial concentration. Moreover, for low initial concentration the van Dongen-Ernst homogeneity exponent is approximately equal to 0 (the slope is close to 1) as it was expected (this kind of behavior was observed in the experiments for dilute systems and/or short aggregation times [22-24]) . For higher ϕ values one can observe deviation from 0

connected with a transition to faster aggregation kinetic especially for longer time (time which corresponds to the kinetic transition depends on the concentration). It can be explained by taking under consideration periodic boundary conditions and by the fact that for higher ϕ ($\phi > 0.1$) the fractals growth is very fast and approach boundaries of the simulated system. In this case a particle which builds up cluster (near the boundary) “does not know” which part of the cluster will be built. Moreover it does not know that it is all the time the same cluster. In simulation this fact manifests itself by deviation of λ from 0. One can treat it as artifact generated by periodic boundary condition (interaction of growing cluster with itself) but on the other hand one can conclude that this situation mimics behavior of a multifractal system. Similar behavior of cluster growth was evidenced in experimental studies [24] where the rate of the cluster growth as a function of electrolyte- and colloid-concentration was investigated.

Another interesting aspect of the dynamics of fractal growth is how the shape of the cluster changes with time. The shape of the cluster can be characterized by the eigenvalues of gyration tensor (which is very similar to the tensor of inertia). For a cluster, the elements of the radius of gyration tensor T are given by:

$$T_{kl} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (r_{ik} - r_{cm,k})(r_{il} - r_{cm,l}) \quad (8)$$

Figure 6 Mass of the cluster as a function of time for various initial concentrations of particles which constitute the cluster.

where k and l are the coordinates x and y , r_{ik} is the k -th coordinates of the position \vec{r}_i and $r_{cm,k}$ is the k -th coordinate of the cluster center-of-mass. The tensor T has two eigenvalues, which are denoted by λ_1 and λ_2 with the convention $\lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2$ and which fulfill the relation

$$R_g^2 = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2 \quad (9)$$

For $\lambda_1 \approx \lambda_2$ the cluster is disk-like. When the difference between λ_1 and λ_2 increases, the

Figure 7. a) Eigenvalues of the tensor T , λ_1 and λ_2 as a function of time for two initial concentrations of particles which constitute the cluster: $\phi=0.05$ and $\phi=0.20$. b) Asphericity as a function of time for two initial concentrations of particles which constitute the cluster: $\phi=0.05$ and $\phi=0.20$.

cluster becomes elliptic. To describe geometrical properties of complex objects one can use a quantity called asphericity A_2 which can be calculated as

$$A_2 = \frac{\langle (\lambda_2 - \lambda_1)^2 \rangle}{\langle (\lambda_2 + \lambda_1)^2 \rangle} \quad (10)$$

It means that $A_2=1$ for a rod like shape and $A_2=0$ for a disk. At the beginning the cluster growth is aspherical because λ_1 is distinctly greater than λ_2 (see Fig. 7a and Fig 7b). The time when the character of fractal growth becomes spherical ($\lambda_1 \approx \lambda_2$, $A_2 \approx 0$) depends on the initial concentration i.e. it is longer for lower initial concentration ϕ .

Conclusion

Our results obtained using the DLL model to simulate the random fractal growth are in good agreement with previous findings. For small concentration of particles building up the cluster, the fractal dimension $d_f = 1.70-1.73$ was obtained. This is in very good agreement with the values obtained by the DLA method. The fractal dimension increases rapidly (for $\phi > 0.1$) with increasing initial concentration of particles. The dynamic of cluster growth is in good agreement with the predictions based on Smoluchowski equation for diffusion limited cluster aggregation and the rate of aggregation strongly depends on the initial concentration of the particles which build up the cluster. In the initial phase of growth the fractal is aspherical.

Our preliminary studies on stochastic fractal growth using simulation based on DLL model indicate that we can obtain the consistent picture of the aggregation process (both structural and dynamic properties) using one simulation method.

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References

1. T. A. Witten, L. M. Sander, Phys. Rev. Lett. **47**, 1400, (1981).
2. T. A. Witten, L. M. Sander, Phys. Rev. B **27**, 5686, (1983).
3. P. Meakin, Phys. Rev. Lett. **51**, 1119, (1983).
4. P. Meakin, J. Chem. Phys. **83**, 3645, (1985).
5. M. Kolb, J. Phys. A. **19**, L263, (1986).
6. R. Jullien, R. Botet, and P. M. Mors, Farad. Disc. Chem. Soc. **83**, 125, (1987).
7. W. D. Brown, R. C. Ball J. Phys. A. **18**, L517, (1987).
8. N. Nazzarro, F. Nieto, A. J. Ramirez-Pastor, Surf. Sci. **497**, 275, (2002).
9. C., I. Mendoza, C. M. Marques, Physica A. **335**, 305, (2004).
10. A. C. Balazs, C. Anderson and M Mathukumar, Macromolecules. **20**, 1999, (1987); A. Chakrabarti, R. Toral. J. Chem. Phys. **91**, 5687, (1989).
11. D. Tillberg, J. Machta, **69**, 51403, (2004).
12. T. Pakula and J. Teichmann, Mat. Res. Soc. Symp. Proc. **455**, 211 (1997); T. Pakula, J. Mol. Liquids **86**, 109 (2000).
13. P. Polanowski, T. Pakula, J. Chem. Phys. **117**, 4022, (2002).
14. P. Polanowski, T. Pakula, J. Chem. Phys. **118**, 11139, (2003).
15. P. Polanowski, T. Pakula, J. Chem. Phys. **120**, 6306, (2004).
16. P. Polanowski, Z. Koza, Phys. Rev. E. **74**, 36103, (2006).
17. T. Visek, Fractal Growth Phenomena, World Scientific, (1989); S. Tolman, P. Meakin Phys. Rev. A, **40**, 428, (1989).
18. Ch. M. Sorensen, G. C. Roberts, J. Col. Interf. Sci. **186**, 447, (1997).
19. M. Smoluchowski, Phys. Z. Chem, **92**, 129, (1917).
20. R. Jullien, R. Botet, Aggregation and Fractal Aggregates, World Scientific, Singapore, (1987).
21. P. Van Dongen, M. H. Ernst, Phys. Rev. Lett. **54**, 1396, (1985).
22. J. Zhang, J. Buffle, Coll. Surf. **107**, 175, (1995).
23. A. Fernandez-Barbero, A. Schmitt, M. Cabrerizo-Vilchez, R. Martinez-Garcia, Physica A **230**, 53, (1996).
24. R. Brunner, S. Gall, W. Wilke, M. Zrinyi, Physica A **239**, 477, (1997).